

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Rhenium with Benzyl dimethylphenylammonium Chloride

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The methods available for the spectrophotometric determination of rhenium are limited. The thiocyanate method suffers from the disadvantage that the complex cannot be extracted into the non-oxygenated organic solvents and the selectivity of the method is poor. Here we report a spectrophotometric method for the determination of rhenium using benzyl dimethylphenylammonium (BDPA) chloride. The use of BDPA in the determination of a number of metal ions has been reported¹. In the present investigation, it is found that in presence of BDPA, the ion-association complex formed between a hexakis(isothiocyanato) rhenium(IV) anion² and a benzyl dimethylphenylammonium cation is completely extractable into chloroform and the sensitivity and selectivity of the method is vastly improved. We have also found that addition of little amount of dimethylformamide enhances the stability and intensifies the colour.

Results and Discussion

By reduction of $[\text{ReO}_4]^-$ with tin(II) ion in hydrochloric acid in presence of thiocyanate ion, the well characterised and stable hexakis(isothiocyanato)rhenium(IV) anion is formed which is not extractable into chloroform or any non-oxygenated organic solvent. In the presence of benzyl dimethyl-

phenylammonium chloride, a quaternary ammonium salt, an ion-association complex is formed which is completely extractable into chloroform by a single extraction. The extracted species has maximum absorbance at 432 nm. Beer's law is obeyed for 0.13–6.6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of rhenium. The Sandell's sensitivity is 0.0045 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and is constant when the acidity of the aqueous solution is kept in the range 0.2–0.3 M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The molar absorptivity is $4.11 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The stannous chloride concentration of the aqueous solution should be in the range 0.006–0.008 M . The benzyl dimethylphenylammonium ion has a marked influence on the extraction of the coloured species into the organic layer. Its concentration should not exceed 0.001 M in the aqueous phase, otherwise precipitation will occur and extraction will be time-consuming. Addition of dimethylformamide is best done after addition of chloroform. The addition of dimethylformamide (0.5–1 ml) is found to play a significant role in increasing stability and colour intensity of the extracted species. The concentration of dimethylformamide is maintained between 3.5 and 7.0% with respect to aqueous phase. If it is below 3.5%, absorbance values are less and colour intensity of the extracted species decreases gradually. If the concentration of dimethylformamide is above 7% and

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upto 17.5% with respect to aqueous phase, there is no significant change in the absorbance value but when the concentration is above 17.5%, the absorbance value slightly decreases. The absorbance remains constant over a period of about 24 h.

The maximum absorbance of the ion-association complex of Re is at 432 nm, where the absorbance due to reagent blank is negligible.

To study the effects of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour, rhenium(VII) (Re taken 33 μg) was extracted and determined according to the recommended procedure in presence of a number of representative foreign ions. The tolerance limit for interferences (in mg) was set at the amount required to cause an error not exceeding 3% in the determination of rhenium: Mn^{II}, Ni^{II} (6.0 each); As^{III} (1.5); Co^{II}, Cd (1.0 each); Zn^{II} (0.98), Hg^{II} (7.0), Pb^{II} (0.65), Cr^{III} (0.528), W^{VI} (0.5), Ag^I (0.4), Sb^{III} (0.2), V^V (0.136), Ir^{III} (0.07), Bi^{III} (0.012), Rh^{III} (0.01), Pd^{II} (0.003); Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Au^{III} (0.002 each); Fe^{III}, Mo^{VI} (0.0 each); bromide (7.0), iodide (6.9), fluoride (5.5); oxalate, acetate (5.0 each); EDTA (7.0), phosphate (1.0); thiosulphate, cyanide (0.5 each); thiourea (0.2). The upper limit of foreign ion concentration was, however, restricted to 200-fold (w/w) excess of the rhenium concentration. The tolerance limits for some of the interfering species could be improved by use of masking agents, e.g. Hg^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Bi^{III} with iodide, Fe^{III} with fluoride, Au^{III} with cyanide, and Cu^{II} and Mo^{VI} require prior removal by extraction with 0.1% oxine solution in chloroform.

The method was applied for determination of rhenium in different synthetic mixtures. The results obtained in each case are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES*

Sl. no	Composition of mixture and amount taken (μg)	Recovery of Re (μg)
1.	Re ^{VII} (33), Pd ^{II} (25), Co ^{II} (850), Pb ^{II} (640)	33.9
2.	Re ^{VII} (33), Cu ^{II} (350), Ni ^{II} (1000), Ir ^{III} (65)	32.1
3.	Re ^{VII} (33), Cd ^{II} (900), Cr ^{III} (265), Fe ^{III} (350)	33.3
4.	Re ^{VII} (33), Bi ^{III} (1200), Pt ^{IV} (390), Sb ^{III} (1700)	33.1
5.	Re ^{VII} (33), Mo ^{VI} (82), As ^{III} (150), Mn ^{II} (850)	33.8

*Extraction was done using masking agent KI in case of sl. nos. 1 and 4 and using KF in case of sl. no. 3. Prior removal of Cu^{II} in sl. no. 2 and Mo^{VI} in sl. no. 5 was done by extraction with 0.1% oxine solution in chloroform

A standard solution containing 33 μg of rhenium was estimated 20-times by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.732 with a standard deviation of 0.008 absorbance unit and relative error of 1.09%.

Thus the present method proves to be simple, sensitive and selective and provides excellent recovery of rhenium in presence of most of the common ions. The present method is far superior to the existing thiocyanate method in precision, accuracy and improved selectivity and the method can be applied to determine rhenium in the mixtures.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-3210 spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

The chemicals used were of analytical grade. A stock solution of rhenium (661.8 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared from potassium perrhenate in 0.02 M HCl and standardised³. The reagent benzyldimethylphenylammonium chloride was prepared by mixing equimolar amounts of benzyl chloride and dimethylaniline, allowing the mixture to stand and the resulting solid was washed with acetone and recrystallised from alcohol. A 0.004 M solution of BDPA in distilled water was used.

To an aliquot of the test solution containing 1.3–66 μg of rhenium(VII), 4 M HCl (1 ml) and 0.09 M stannous chloride solution (1 ml) were added. To this mixture, were added 1 M potassium thiocyanate (2 ml), 0.004 M BDPA (1 ml) solutions and adequate amount of distilled water so that the acidity of the solution was in the range 0.2–0.3 M with respect to HCl and its volume was about 14 ml. To it chloroform (10 ml) was added and the mixture was shaken for 1 min and then dimethylformamide (0.5 ml) was added and again shaken for 0.5 min. The organic layer was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance of the extract was measured at 432 nm. A calibration curve was prepared in the same manner from which rhenium content in unknown solutions was computed.

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